

THE VALIDITY AND ROLE OF IMPROVING THE MEDICAL CULTURE OF THE POPULATION IN SOCIAL LIFE

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ABSTRACT

Today, the relevance of social life is gaining importance. People's health, healthy thinking, knowledge and skills in the society that surrounds us. The breadth of mind is important. Because being able to use social networks, which are becoming a part of our life, in the right and necessary form is an important factor for every person.

The relevance of improving the medical culture of the population today in social life and the expressions of reflection in the mass media are researched in the article. Nowadays, the Uzbek media space is of particular importance due to its promptness, truthfulness and coverage of current topics. In this regard, in order to develop, rise, grow, keep up with the times, and achieve huge milestones in all areas, separate comprehensive works are being carried out in each area. Within the framework of the research, the peculiarities and methods of specialized journalism were analyzed.

Key words: *mass communications, socio-economic, architecture, mass media, inclusive, pluralistic, public information.*

INTRODUCTION

The types of information that people receive are as diverse as the world around us. In addition to simple, everyday life information, a person works through certain organized information. These include educational information, professional information, scientific information, artistic and aesthetic information and others. In the management of society, specific types of information are used - socio-political, international, military, secret and other types of information. Social information has a special place among them. Social information consists of providing information about society for society. [M. Khudoykulov, 2011, 30-33].

The 21st century is recognized as the "age of information communications" by the world community. In such conditions, ownership of knowledge and information allows to dominate production and economic relations. Due to the introduction of

computer culture, a new way of thinking and acquiring knowledge has emerged, based on a person's desire to work on himself and improve his skills. [N. Kasimova, N. Toshpolatova, N. Shofayzieva, N. Muratova, 2008, 5-6].

Today, the Internet and modern mass media are developing rapidly. In the conditions of the Internet and modern media, anyone can be an author and distributor of information. To implement this type of activity, the world community is developing ways to create equal opportunities for everyone to use the means of information. Governments are working on this and are introducing into their legislation various norms that regulate legal relations in the field of information exchange, the right to receive and distribute information, and the obligations and responsibilities of individuals for published materials. [I.V. Zhilavskoy, 2015, 236].

Although Internet media has become popular in many developed countries of the world, the number of printed publications in them is correspondingly enviable. Organization of day-to-day work on strengthening the healthy environment among the population, forming a culture of healthy living, as well as acting as centers for the improvement of medical culture in the conditions of reforming the health care system, living among the population formation of culture, directly dealing with the issues of raising the medical culture of the family and wider involvement of the mass media in this field serve as an important factor in the development of the field.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Since the emergence of medicine as an independent field, it has been developing in harmony not only with medical and technical sciences, but also with philosophy, religion, and artistic mastery of existence. Acquaintance with creativity, poetry and fiction increases the specialist's direct theoretical and practical experience, covers it with spiritual and emotional feelings. Many doctors became great philosophers and writers. This is evidenced by the fact that Ibn Sino, the father of medicine, was a poet and a writer together with his great medicine.

Alisher Navoi does not limit himself to expressing his practical tips for achieving health in the hundreds of works of art that he has created. He also seeks measures to record the necessary points regarding the scientific-theoretical direction of the medical field. In particular, the previous part of the work called "Mahbubul Qulub" (Beloved by Hearts, 1500) called the 15th chapter "Atibba Zikrida" ("About Physicians"). This article begins like this: "A physician needs delicacy in his science, and his patients need compassion and grace." [A.Navoi,1998,14-23].

So, from the very first sentence, the scholar demands that a medical professional should be skilled in his work, treat patients with compassion, and later, be gentle in his words and have the ability to entertain. With this, the writer Luqmani continues the

teachings of Ibn Sina. It is a fact confirmed by life experience that a person who envies medicine must, on the one hand, master his profession perfectly, and on the other hand, find a way to the patient's heart.

Erkin Vahidov, one of the bright representatives of modern Uzbek national literature, says: If we talk about the essence of poetry, according to the opinion of philosophers, poetry is a phenomenon of polyvalence, that is, it creates a new quality when combined with other arts and phenomena. And this energetic force manifests itself separately from its own force and from the force of unified reality. Healing means getting rid of the disease, recovery, and the word doctor means a doctor who cures the disease. We need to act so that information and works of art serve as an effective tool in the outlook and education of young people who have set themselves the goal of treating human health and psyche. [E.Vahidov, 2019,755].

The famous Russian writer Anton Pavlovich Chekhov, in the story "The 6th Ward": the example of the life of doctors is the indifference and lack of sympathy in society, ignorance and ignorance, the lack of desire to take responsibility for their actions, deeds, loneliness. Cruel and unfair treatment of patients is in harmony not only with the life of prisoners and exiles, but also with the strict order of Russian society ruled by Emperor Alexander III. In this, a conscious person with his own opinion is powerless. There is also a hint of this meaning in the name of the story. The 6th house remains a scary place for free-thinking people with their own worldview. The author shows that a society that lives only for the benefit of consumerism will decline. People who are drowned in selfishness and self-interest do not feel the need for spiritual and intellectual development. He emphasized the opinions that the exchange of life values leads the society to a dead end against various new changes. [Ziya for those who want knowledge,2011,204]¹.

DISCUSSION

Doctor of philology, Professor Fayzulla Mominov writes that the first need for information exchange arose due to the coordination of the management of the upper classes in the Roman Empire. Widespread political information exchanges focused mainly on economic, personal, household, and awareness goals rather than political action. News about the government's decisions are written on plasterboards. Everything is not written here in detail, which reflects the tradition of written journalism, that is, "the government is not told anything about the facts that are unfavorable." Only after the 15th century, plasterboards began to be replaced by light, convenient and speedy paper sheets. [F. Mominov, 2019, 428-429].

¹ <https://ziyouz.uz/jahon-nasri/anton-chexov/>. Bosh sahifa. Jahon nasri onlayn antologiyasi. Ziyo istagan qalblar uchun. 2004-2021. Portal O'zbekiston Matbuot va axborot agentligi tomonidan 27.07.2011 da ro'yxatga olingan. Guvohnoma № 0677

Specialization in journalism is one of the most complex and urgent issues. Scientists such as Tamber and Prentiss, Weber, and Durkheim, the fathers of sociology, distinguished each other according to their specialization and main role. It is a difficult matter to sharply demarcate or differentiate between specializations in journalism. Because journalism itself is defined differently in scientific literature. The issue of specialization in journalism was first clarified by researchers such as Halling and Mancini. Halling's views are based on: Journalism is neutral from purely commercial and political factors. In addition, journalism differs from specific professions such as traditional fields such as law, medicine, architecture, and engineering. Halling and Mancini focus on the following as the main activities of journalistic activity: independent activity, clear professional norms and public service. [Karin Wahl-Jorgensen, Thomas Hanitzsch, 2009, 48].

As today's Uzbek journalism enters the architecture of the world information space as a structural department, the issue of introducing the use of modern genres and forms of information is the need of the hour. That is, it is not recommended to over-embellish the informational text and use words excessively. For example, all the modern genres emerging in the world information field are focused on brevity and speed. The era of old, liquid or amorphous (dead) methods has passed [J. Razzakov, 2020, 38]¹.

Currently, extensive works are being carried out in each field. For example, if we take the wide-ranging reforms implemented in the field of medicine, a number of laws and decisions are being implemented in order to strengthen the health of the population, to form a medical culture and to widely introduce a healthy lifestyle among people. All this is for human dignity, because healthy thoughts are formed in a healthy environment. With the initiatives of our honorable President, human dignity is being recognized at a high level of value. It is the duty of each of us to create a healthy environment and create a foundation for the young generations who are our future.

In the context of the pandemic, which is becoming a global problem worldwide, the prevention of disease and regular physical education and mass sports, as well as the formation of life skills for a healthy lifestyle, following the principles of proper nutrition, healthy serves to form a healthy lifestyle.

We live in an information society. Everyone is busy with their work. However, the need for information will never disappear. The consumer of information always receives only the messages that are of interest to him. The journalist requires that the information he transmits should be accurate and complete. [E.P. Prokhorov, 2005,6].

¹ Razzaqov J. "O`qish boshqa, uqish boshqa". <https://pv.uz/>. 2020 y, 2 may.

Forming a modern journalistic mindset, preparing a journalist for practical, creative activity that meets the demands of the mass media system is one of the most important tasks of today. [A.V.Parshakova,2013,14].

In today's information-saturated society and borderless exchange of information, the issue of journalists' impartiality and media literacy is extremely important.

CONCLUSION

The role of the mass media in improving the medical culture of the population in Uzbekistan is incomparable. Because the interesting programs and broadcasts transmitted by radio and television, the formation of a healthy lifestyle in families, the improvement of medical culture among the residents of the neighborhood and the youth, and the role of centers for the improvement of medical culture in the context of reforming the health care system, the population forming a culture of life among people, directly dealing with the issues of improving the medical culture of the family and wider involvement of mass media in this field is directly related to the fact that it serves as an important factor in the development of the field.

In accordance with the established procedures, it will be appropriate if work is carried out on the basis of suggestions and recommendations based on the demand of the time to process the information resources they have collected and deliver them to the general public. The increase in the medical culture of the population is not only the main factor for the longevity of citizens, but also the social stability of the society, in particular, the education of a perfect person.

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